

Diluted Tributyl Phosphate as an Extractant for Cadmium

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TRIBUTYL phosphate (TBP) was used as an extractant for several elements including cadmium in iodide media but common elements like mercury, zinc, and bismuth were coextracted along with cadmium¹. Cadmium was extracted from thiocyanate medium but cobalt, zinc, bismuth, showed strong interference in such extraction². The extraction of cadmium with undiluted TBP from hydrochloric acid containing 0.5M lithium chloride was incomplete³ due to low salting-out concentration. Thus systematic studies on the solvent extraction of cadmium with TBP is lacking. Hence this paper presents such studies. 45% TBP in benzene was used for the extraction from 2M hydrochloric acid containing 2M lithium chloride as the salting-out agent. Cadmium from the organic phase was stripped with water and was determined photometrically at 510 nm with 4-(2-pyridylazo)-resorcinol (PAR)⁴. The method was extended for the analysis of cadmium in Wood's metal and silver brazing alloy.

Experimental

Apparatus and Reagents : Type FEK-57 photoelectric colorimeter, wrist action flask shaken, digital pH meter (ECIL, India) with glass and calomel reference electrode.

About 1.30 g of cadmium oxide (A. R., Renald) was dissolved in 10 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid and the volume made up to 250 ml with distilled water. The solution was standardized complexometrically⁵ and was found to contain 4.5 mg/ml of cadmium. The dilute solution containing 4.5 μ g/ml of cadmium was prepared by thousand fold dilution.

Tributyl phosphate (B.D.H. England), b.p., 143°
4-(2-pyridylazo)-resorcinol (PAR): 0.05% aqueous solution.

The buffer solution of pH 10 was prepared by dissolving 21 g of ammonium chloride in distilled water, and mixed with 140 ml of concentrated ammonia (28%). The total volume was made up to one litre with distilled water.

General Procedure : An aliquot of solution containing 9 μ g of cadmium was taken. Hydrochloric acid and lithium chloride were added such that the final concentration of both the acid and the salting-out agent in 25 ml of solution was 2M each. The solution was transferred to a separatory funnel.

Then ml of 45% TBP in benzene was added. The solution was shaken on a wrist action flask shaken for 5 min. The two layers were allowed to settle and separate. The aqueous layer was carefully withdrawn and it was discarded. From the organic phase cadmium was stripped with 10 and 5 ml portions of distilled water. To the combined aqueous phase 2 ml of 0.05% PAR and 5 ml of buffer solution of pH 10 were added. The orange-red complex of cadmium-PAR was measured photometrically at 510 nm with 10 mm glass cuvettes. The concentration of cadmium was computed from the calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

Effect of Acidity and Tributyl Phosphate Concentration : The concentration of hydrochloric acid was varied from 0.5-60M. Tributyl phosphate concentration was varied from 15-100% (0.54M-3.66M) with benzene as the diluent. The results indicated that 45% TBP was adequate for the quantitative extraction of cadmium from 2-4M hydrochloric acid containing 2M lithium as the salting-out agent. An attempt was also made to ascertain the probable nature of the complex by plotting the graph of log D vs log[TBP]. The slope was 1.91 and 2.35 at 1.0 and 1.5M hydrochloric acid. This shows that the extracted species is disolvated and is of the type $CdCl_2 \cdot 2TBP$. Benzene was found to be the most suitable diluent. Other solvents tried were toluene, xylene, chloroform, and hexane but the maximum extraction co-efficient was noted with 45% TBP in benzene.

Effect of Salting-out Agents :

The salts of alkali metals like chloride of lithium, sodium, potassium and ammonium were tested as salting-out agents (1-3M) at various acidities of 1-4M. Cadmium was quantitatively extracted from 2M lithium chloride containing 2-4M hydrochloric acid. It was found that the extraction was not quantitative in the presence of other salting-out agents. Hence 2M lithium chloride in 2M hydrochloric acid is recommended as the salting-out agent for the extraction of cadmium.

Period of Extraction :

The period of extraction was varied from 1 to 15 min. It was found that the extraction was quantitative within 5 min of shaking.

Effect of Diverse Ions :

Various ions were tested to study their interference during the extraction of cadmium (Table-I). The tolerance limit was set at the amount of foreign ion required to cause $\pm 2\%$ error in the recovery of cadmium. It was found that cadmium was extracted quantitatively in presence of 1000 fold excess of

TABLE—1 EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS

Cd = 9 μ g ; LiCl = 2M ; HCl = 2M ; 45% TBP in Benzene

Tolerance limit 1 \times 10 ³ μ g	Diverse Ions
10	Ca ²⁺ , Ba ²⁺ , Sr ²⁺ , Mg ²⁺ , Be ²⁺ , SO ₄ ²⁻ , NO ₃ ⁻ , AsO ₄ ³⁻ , SCN ⁻ , EDTA ⁴⁻ , Tart ³⁻ , Malo ²⁻ , C ₂ O ₄ ²⁻ , Thiourea
7.5	Cs ⁺ , Rb ⁺ , Al ³⁺
5.0	Ru ³⁺ , Rh ³⁺ , Ir ³⁺ , Bi ³⁺ , Cr ³⁺ , Ti ⁴⁺ , Ge ⁴⁺ , TeO ₃ ²⁻ , SeO ₃ ²⁻ , Mo ₇ O ₂₄ ⁴⁻ , F ⁻ , Ascorbate ⁻
2.5	Au ³⁺ , Pd ²⁺ , Pt ⁴⁺ , Hg ²⁺ , Os ³⁺ , Sn ²⁺ , WO ₄ ²⁻
2.0	Mn ²⁺ , Sn ²⁺ , VO ₃ ²⁻ , UO ₂ ²⁺
1.0	Ga ³⁺ , In ³⁺ , Tl ³⁺ , Sc ³⁺ , Zr ⁴⁺ , ReO ₄ ⁻ , Fe ³⁺ , Cu ²⁺ , Ni ²⁺ , Co ³⁺
0.5	Zn ²⁺ , A ⁺⁺

alkali and alkaline earth metals and common complexing anions. Platinum group metals, oxy-anions, bismuth, and chromium were tolerated in the ratio 1 : 500. Gallium, indium, thallium, scandium, and zirconium were tolerated in 1 : 1000 ratio. However, bromide, iodide and dichromate showed strong interference. The tolerance limit of some of the ions were enhanced by selective extraction with mesityl oxide^{6,7} (UO₂²⁺, Fe³⁺), acetylacetone⁸ (Cu²⁺), dimethyl glyoxime⁸ (Ni²⁺) and TBP⁸ (Zn²⁺).

Application to the Analysis of Wood's Metal and Silver Brazing Alloy.

About 0.1 g of the alloy was dissolved in 10 ml of 1 : 1 nitric acid. It was digested on a water bath for half an hour and tin was precipitated as metastannic acid. It was filtered, ignited and weighed as oxide. The filtrate was made up to 100 ml. Then 1 ml of an aliquot was taken and 2 ml each of 25% sodium thiosulphate and 10% citric acid solution were added. The concentration of hydrochloric acid was adjusted to 0.5M. Lead from the aqueous phase was extracted with 0.01M diethylammonium dithiocarbamate in chloroform. The aqueous phase containing cadmium was withdrawn and it was extracted and determined as per the general procedure. The amount of cadmium found was 13.27% and 13.05% as against the reported value of 13.5%.

A sample of silver brazing alloy was dissolved and brought into solution as per the above procedure. An aliquot of 2.5 ml of this solution was taken and was adjusted to pH 5.0 and copper was extracted with pure acetylacetone. The aqueous phase containing silver, cadmium and zinc was carefully withdrawn and zinc was extracted at pH 2-4 in presence of 0.5M sodium thiocyanate with 10 ml of 10% TBP in benzene. From the aqueous phase cadmium was extracted as per the general procedure. Silver remained in the aqueous phase. The amount of cadmium found was 21.18% and 21.58% as against 21.3%.

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Some Organothallium(III) Dithiocarbamates

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It has been recently suggested that the dithiocarbamate moiety acts as a bidentate group in R₃Tl(III)⁴⁺²⁻, RTl(III)³⁻ and Tl(III)⁴⁻ dithiocarbamates (R=Me or Et). We report in this communication the preparation and characterisation of some new arylthallium(III) dithiocarbamates of the formulae R₃Tl(dtc) and RTl(dtc)₂ (R=phenyl or *p*-tolyl), in which the dtc group acts as monodentate and the compounds possess an ester type structure.

Experimental

Sodium diethyl and dimethyl dithiocarbamates were obtained from Alfa Inorganics. Sodium or ammonium salts of phenyl- and benzyldithiocarbamic acids and that of morpholine-N-carbodi-thioate were prepared by a reported method⁵. Organothallium halides were prepared through known methods⁶. Typical preparations are given below :

Diphenylthallium(III) diethyldithiocarbamate :

An aqueous solution of sodium diethyldithiocarbamate (10 mmole) was added to a suspension of diphenylthallium(III) chloride (10 mmole) in benzene (50 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred for two hours and then refluxed for one hour. The two layers were separated. The organic layer after distilling off excess solvent under reduced pressure gave a white crystalline solid, which was washed several times with water and dried. It was recrystallised from petroleum ether (60-80°) and finally dried under vacuum.